

A Study On Satisfaction Level Of Management Students Through Online Mode In Gurugram

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is to examine the satisfaction level of management students through online education. The factors include faculty's knowledge and facilitation, course design and platform availability. The use of primary data is done to collect information through surveys and interviews. The respondents were management students from Gurugram. This paper ends with hands-on recommendations to enhance online learning. This study would contribute to the existing literature.

Keywords

Management Students, Satisfaction Levels, Online Education.

Introduction

Background and rationale of the study

Education plays a paramount role in the success of development of any nation. On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID 19, a pandemic. [1] On March 24, 2020, our country, India came under complete lock down for 21 days. [2] Such Lockdown was never seen before excepting in the year 1984 during the riots that too in Delhi and nearby areas and just for few days. This time the entire nation was under Lockdown. The Coronavirus impacted every part of the human life and therefore there was unavoidable impact on education as well. The educational institutes, schools and colleges were forced to close as well. The schools and institutes were forced to conduct online classes. Due to closure, the students had no option but to study online. The face-to-face interaction/on-site education came to a halt completely. The online education was earlier there as well. Before pandemic, only few educational institutes had adopted online or blended learning methods. After pandemic, it started catering to world-wide population.

Therefore, with online's growing acceptance and need, it is essential to gauge the satisfaction level of students through online mode as Empirical studies conducted earlier, with structural model applied, have shown that satisfaction is an important predictor of learning outcome. Student satisfaction is widely cited as a measure of effectiveness of online education system (Alavi, Wheeler, and Valacich, 1995, Graham & Scarborough, 2001). [3][4] Learners' satisfaction has been shown to be positively correlated with quality of learning outcomes. Keeping in mind the online context, an understanding of the factors that influence student satisfaction can be used as an input to the apt design of learning environments. This would also positively influence the experience of online learning of the targeted students. Therefore, the study will help the educationist to help identify and strengthen the factors to enhance the students' experience in terms of online learning especially during pandemic. Moreover, it is important to explore more in defining the elements of satisfaction which is multifaceted and quite dynamic in nature.

This study is specifically on the Post Graduate Management students of Gurugram who faced the repercussions like all the other educational institutes. These Post Graduate students is an important segment of education as they contribute to employment as most businesses are welcoming employees with greater number of degrees and a wider range of knowledge. The students are trained and tutored to excel in every part of the job. There is hardly any data is available to show their satisfaction level even though they are important segment of the student population. Hence, it is essential to study the satisfaction level of the students at management institutes on online education which would further help to strengthen the positive factors and improve the area of negative factors that led to the dissatisfaction.

Research Questions

The study will focus on the following questions:

1. How satisfied are students with online education?
2. What factors contribute to the satisfaction level of the students with online education?
3. What factors contribute to the dissatisfaction level of the students with online education?

Objective of study

The study will focus on the following objectives:

1. To study the satisfaction level of management students through online education.
2. To study the factors that contribute to the satisfaction level of the students with online education.
3. To study the factors that contribute to the dissatisfaction level of the students with online education.

Review of Literature

Faculty's Knowledge and Facilitation

Everyone has a favourite teacher and hence the teacher or the faculty's role is an essential ingredient in satisfying the needs of a student whether in offline or online classes. Tinggui Chen et al. (2020) mentioned in their study that two-way interaction of teaching must be improved. [5]

Aleksander Aristovnik et al. (2020) mentioned teachers must organise their content according to the new mode of delivery so that students should not feel isolated in the learning process. In context to their academic work, students were asked about teachers' responsiveness and whether they were provided with timely assignments through online mode. The students answered it affirmatively adding to that they mentioned the teachers had been preparing regular assignments and even answered to their questions and were open to their suggestions. The report suggested that students were most satisfied with the support provided by the teaching staff and their universities' public relations. The study further showed that regardless of the continent, the students were satisfied with the overall teaching staff. [6]

Claudiu Coman et al. (2020), an online survey based on a semi structured questionnaire was conducted and data was collected from the two of the largest Romanian Universities. Technical issues were the most important followed by the teachers' lack of technical skills and their teaching style improperly adapted to the online environment. Also, lack of interaction with teachers or poor communication were also identified as a major problem. Students, teachers, and universities were not prepared for sudden shift to online learning and teaching, however they tried to find strategies to adapt and meet the new challenges. Students stated that teachers used a limited number of tools provided by the courses; they used only the basic tools which were almost mandatory for conducting the courses. [7]

Course Design

The course design expresses the rigidity or flexibility of the program's educational objectives, teaching strategies, and evaluation methods. It describes the extent to which an education program can accommodate or be responsive to each learner's individual needs. Viewed as important variable that influences students' perceptions about online courses, the elements in the course design or the ways in which the teaching program is structured so that it can be delivered through various communication media.

Arjita Jain et al (2025) shows the study tells that faculty and students agree that technology impacts instructional effectiveness and creative course design includes various learning pedagogies to positively influence academic performance. [8]

Sonali Chettri, et al. (2020), the findings of the study concludes that majority of the students are satisfied with the content provision by the faculty in the form of PDF format, multimedia presentations and the word document. [9]

Platform Availability and Others

Mohammad Mahyoob et al. (2021) in his study evaluated the learners' experience in online education and to assess the viability of the virtual methods of learning which was achieved by analysing the learners' responses to the survey-based questionnaire. He found that the teachers' recordings can be made available which was the advantage of online learning, therefore, students can access and understand the lesson better. Though challenges like writing and speaking (interaction with the information technology) were found as not all learners had good quality devices nor did they have great network connection. [10]

Mona Sami Hamed (2021) studied "the experiences, challenges and acceptance of e-learning as a tool for teaching during pandemic among university staff" and concluded technology as a positive step towards evolution and change. The learners agreed on usefulness, ease of use and acceptance of e-learning. [11]

Methodology

Descriptive survey method is used for the present study as it systematically and accurately describes the present status of the research work. The population for the study will be 528. The sample, in this study, comprises 100 students of the management students studying in Gurugram region. In this study, Random sampling method was followed to draw the sample from the target population.

Tools and techniques used for data collection

A structured questionnaire was made in Google form. The questionnaire has closed ended and open-ended questions which were filled by the students. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first section is about the demographic profile of the

students (age, gender and whether the classes being held online). The second section included the closed ended questions based on satisfaction level of the students with the online mode based on The Faculty Facilitation, Course Design and Platform Availability. The closed ended questions followed the Likert Scale in which the variables were assessed on the five-point scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. A closed ended question on to check the students' satisfaction level was also asked. The third section is open ended questions related with the factors that led to the satisfaction and dissatisfaction level of the students with the online mode. A structured Questionnaire for an interview was also made to collect data from 50 students through Convenient Sampling technique. A structured interview was conducted in which same type of questions were presented in the same order to each student. The wordings were specified. The questions were both a combination of closed ended questions and open ended. It helped to validate the data further collected through Google forms.

Procedure of the data collection

The questionnaire as mentioned earlier was designed on Google platform i.e., Google form and was sent to students via WhatsApp groups and received back from them within a period of a month. The one-on-one interview between the researcher and the students was conducted as well.

The students were informed about the objective of the study and the methodology to gather the information. The students especially during the interview were assured about the confidentiality of the information. No inducements were given to participate in the study.

The primary sources of data collection were through the structured questionnaires and secondary sources of information were through Blogs, Research papers/journals (National and International) and different websites.

Procedure of data analysis

The data obtained from the students is analysed with the help of both quantitative and qualitative techniques according to the requirement of the study. Data obtained from the close-ended questions is analysed using **Percentage Analysis method (quantitative analysis)**. **Content Analysis** (qualitative analysis) is used to analyse data obtained from open-ended questions. Quantitative data can be used for large sample, it is objective, faster, easier and more cost effective. The quantitative data may not provide the depth and the detail, however the combination of both the analysis can improve assessments as one type of data are well-adjusted by the strength of the other. Hence, the reason to select the qualitative analysis as the responses that would be recorded through the interactions of open-ended questions would be more detailed and comprehensive in the form of emotions of students, their thoughts, and experiences in their natural settings. There is a graphical representation of Quantitative data based on the rating scale designed on the questionnaire and the answers thereby obtained through them. Further, the data would be analysed and interpreted. The techniques of Qualitative Content Analysis include Summarizing, Explicative and Structuring Content Analysis.

Result and Discussion

As the research is based on the study on satisfaction level of management students through online education during pandemic in Gurugram region, it is designed as an exploratory study using combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis. The data collected was analysed quantitatively and qualitatively. Responses to close ended questions were analysed quantitatively and responses to two open ended questions were analysed qualitatively. Similarly for the interview format, responses for open ended and close ended questions were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively respectively.

Profile of the Sample Respondents

The section provides the basic information of the college students. The following table shows the output of the questions related to gender, age group, academic year, Level of study, the location of the College and whether the classes were held online or not. A structured questionnaire was developed on Google form and distributed randomly through

social handles. The gender distribution showed the males respondents were 64% and female respondents were 36%. They were 100% post graduate management students. 100% mentioned that their college was in Gurugram. The students are justifiably distributed as per their academic year. 100% of the Second-year students were the respondents. The surveyed statistics showed the respondents were mostly in the age group between 20 and 25 years, 82% to be precise and 18% in the age group between 25 and 30 years 100% respondents mentioned that their classes are being held online. Also, follows the data in a tabular form (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographics

Demographic Profile of the Students		
Parameter		Percentage
Gender	Male	64%
	Female	36%
Post Graduate Management Student	Yes	100%
	No	NIL
Location: Gurgaon	Yes	100%
	No	NIL
Level of Study	First Year	NIL
	Second Year	100%
Age Group (in years)	Less than 20 years	NIL
	20-25 years	82%
	25-30 years	18%
	30-35 years	NIL
Are Management classes being held online?	Yes	100%
	No	NIL

Satisfaction level of management students with online education during Pandemic

100% students mentioned that their classes were held online. When asked about their satisfaction level with online education, most of the students 47% were neutral, 31% were satisfied, 11% were very dissatisfied, 8% were dissatisfied and 3% were very satisfied. The factors like accessibility, flexibility in terms of location, faculty’s facilitation, and course structure and resource availability contributed to the satisfaction level whereas lack of personal attention, hectic schedule, network issues, and long hours of screen time and lack of practical exposure contributed to the dissatisfaction level. The following is the graphical representation of the data.

Satisfaction level

Satisfaction (On a scale of 1-5, please provide information on the following items. 1: Very dissatisfied, 2: dissatisfied, 3: neutral, 4: satisfied, 5: Very satisfied)

The Google form also further included questions divided in three categories. The following is the analysis of **Faculty’s Facilitation**. 8% strongly disagree, 38% agreed, 18% of students mentioned that they strongly agree that the faculty understood the need of the students and delivered the content effectively. 32% were neutral and 4% did not agree.

Students who strongly disagreed were 7%, 39% agreed, 18% strongly agree that the faculty’s communication is clear and full of enthusiasm while delivering through online mode. 32% were neutral and still 4% did not agree. When asked about whether the faculty had complete knowledge of the subject 38% agreed, 25% were neutral and only 2% did not agree and 5% strongly disagreed. 29% strongly agreed. 23% strongly agreed on the usage of webinar. According to the students, the faculty uses the platform to an optimum level to create a comfortable learning space. 8% strongly disagreed and the maximum 37% students agreed. 23% were neutral and the 9% did not agree. When asked about how much individual attention is given when necessary and genuine feedback is provided when required, then 16% strongly agreed, 24% were neutral and 10% did not agree. 8% strongly disagreed and 42% agreed. If we see at all the five parameters, the pattern of the answers show that most students agreed on all the five parameters. Next follows the tabular form of the data. Also, after that is the graphical representation of the data.

Faculty Facilitation

Table 2

Satisfaction level of Management students for Faculty's Facilitation

Particulars	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Facilitation - The faculty understands the need of the students and delivers the content effectively	8%	4%	32%	38%	18%
Communication- The faculty's communication is clear and full of enthusiasm while delivering through online mode	7%	4%	32%	39%	18%
Knowledge- The faculty has complete knowledge of the subject he or she teaches	5%	2%	25%	38%	29%
Webinar Usage- The faculty uses the platform to an optimum level to create a comfortable learning space	8%	9%	23%	37%	23%
Individual attention- Special attention is given when necessary and genuine feedback is provided when required	8%	10%	24%	42%	16%

If we take the average of each column, then Strongly Disagree is 7.2%, Disagree is 5.8%, Neutral is 27.2%, Agree is 38.8% and Strongly Agree is 20.8%. Hence, most of the students agreed and are satisfied.

The following is the analysis of **Course Design** through online mode: 11% strongly agreed that the course structure is designed to generate experience of different learning style for example few leaners like kinesthetics ways of learning, the others are auditory and still others prefer visual style of learning. 9% did not agree and 28% were neutral. 8% strongly disagreed and 44% students agreed. When asked about the coverage in terms of syllabus is appropriate then 11% responded strongly agree 28% answered neutral and 6%strongly disagree. 7% did not agree and 48% agreed. 21%strongly agreed for the content provision is made available in terms of notes/videos, etc. 26% were neutral and 7%strongly disagreed. 4% disagreed and maximum of 42% agreed. 17 % strongly agreed that the Platform is used to create an efficient learning environment. 27% were neutral and 8% strongly disagreed. Disagree is 6% and 42% agreed. Also, in case of the ownership whether the platform courses are designed to be able to take charge/ accountability for the students learning, maximum students i.e., 51%agreed, 21% were neutral and 14%strongly agreed. 5% disagreed and 9% strongly disagreed. If we see at all the five parameters, the pattern of the answers show that most students agreed on all the five parameters. Next follows the tabular form of the data. Also, after that is the graphical representation of the data.

Course Design

Table 3

Satisfaction level of Management students for Course Design (through online mode)

Particulars	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Structure - The course structure is designed to generate experience of different learning style	8%	9%	28%	44%	11%
Coverage- The coverage in terms of syllabus is appropriate	6%	7%	28%	48%	11%
Content Provision- The provision of content is made available in terms of notes/videos, etc.	7%	4%	26%	42%	21%
Webinar Usage- Platform is used to create an efficient learning environment	8%	6%	27%	42%	17%
Ownership- Platform courses are designed to be able to take charge/ accountability for your own learning	9%	5%	21%	51%	14%

If we take the average of each column, then Strongly Disagree is 7.6%, Disagree is 6.2%, Neutral is 26%, Agree is 45.4% and Strongly Agree is 14.8%. Hence, most of the students agreed and are satisfied.

The following is the analysis of **Platform Availability**: Only 9% strongly agreed that the learnability i.e., the steps of online teaching that the students are using are easy to learn as compared to 43% of students who agreed. 33% were neutral and 7% strongly disagreed and 8% disagreed. The navigation system of online network teaching platform is easy, 21% of students strongly agreed and 24% were neutral and only 5% strongly disagreed. 7% disagreed and 43% of students agreed. When asked about the recording of the learning content/ information then the 17%students strongly agreed, 36%agreed and 10% strongly disagreed. 8% did not agree and 29% were neutral.

When asked about the login/ registration as a new user without any hassle. 22%responded strongly agree 27% answered neutral and 7%strongly disagreed, 5% disagreed. 39% agreed. 38%strongly agreed for the learning expectations from the existing functions/ course of online platform. 11%strongly disagreed and 25% were neutral and 11% strongly agreed. Whether the online mode is appealing compared to the offline mode in terms of visuals/videos 11% strongly agreed 32% were neutral and 32% agreed as well and 11%strongly disagreed and 14% disagreed. When asked whether the students would like to continue with the online education and recommend it to others 11% strongly agreed 32% were neutral and 14% strongly disagreed. 26% agreed. Also, in case of the participation in classroom discussion during online teaching the maximum 39%agreed, 31% were neutral and 16%strongly agreed. 10% strongly disagreed and 4% disagreed. If we see at all the parameters, the pattern of the answers show that most students agreed maximum on all the eight parameters except for the willingness to continue with online education where the maximum students were neutral. Next follows the tabular form of the data. Also, after that is the graphical representation of the data.

Platform Availability

Table 4

Satisfaction level of Management students with Platform Availability and others

Particulars	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Learnability - The steps of online teaching platform that you are using are easy to learn	7%	8%	33%	43%	9%
Easy to browse- Navigation system of online network teaching platform is easy.	5%	7%	24%	43%	21%
Record- You can record your learning (any content/information)	10%	8%	29%	36%	17%
Login/ registration - You can login/register as a new user without any hassle	7%	5%	27%	39%	22%
Learning expectations - The existing functions/course of online platform meets your learning expectations	11%	15%	25%	38%	11%
Appealing- Compared to offline mode, online mode is attractive especially in terms of visuals/videos	11%	14%	32%	32%	10%
Willingness- Would like to continue with online education and recommend it to others	14%	16%	32%	26%	11%
Participation- You can participate in classroom discussion during online teaching	10	4	31	39	16%

If we take the average of each column, then Strongly Disagree is 9.3%, Disagree is 9.6%, Neutral is 29.1%, Agree is 37% and Strongly Agree is 14.6%. Hence, most of the students agreed and are satisfied.

The form also included open ended questions with respect to the factors that led to the satisfaction with online education and the factors that led to the dissatisfaction with online education.

The factors that led to the satisfaction level included: Most of the students mentioned about the easy accessibility, easy procedure, easy participation, and the appealing videos. Also, students mentioned about the Breakout rooms that Zoom platform provides. It helps the faculty to give individual attention to the students when activities are conducted in break out rooms. Most students also mentioned about the comfort of the home and time is ample for the self-activities. Online learning is efficient in terms of cost saving and time saving. The finances were utilized for various certification. The students don't have to travel long distances and hence saves on time. Hence, they can do multiple tasks while studying. Online mode is convenient to use. In fact, the presentation skills are enhanced too. Recording of the sessions really helped the students as they could watch and listen to the sessions according to their convenience. Even if they missed the class, they could learn about the session later which led to continuation of learning. It also helped in deep understanding of few topics. Doubts clearing sessions organized by the college and the guest lectures provided enhanced the knowledge further. Also, a student commented that there was an ease of communication through online mediums, ease to learning, information (materials and resources) was easily available and further the convenience in class attendance as well. Overall, it was effective and organized well. The students appreciated that there were extra efforts put by the college faculties in providing the courseware. The faculty was supportive. The course structure was well designed. It was effective and organised well. They liked the animated videos. The online mode was flexible and gave enough time for students to do self-study. The students reach of knowledge widened. It led to technologically learning. The online mode is good for remote learning. The faculties gave individual attention and made the students

familiar with changing work environment. Also, a student mentioned about the effective interface and great visualization. Further, student mentioned that the tougher course set, and syllabus strict marking led to satisfaction as it helped the students to focus more and not deviate from the studies.

The factors that led to the dissatisfaction level included: The classes get hectic at times, there is less or no communication amongst the peer group, there is lack of practical knowledge (assignments), group study and events engagement. The practical aspect became difficult to understand because of the lack of the software. Few topics were unclear. It also restricted the students to develop relationship management skills. A student mentioned it affects the health at times as screen time and usage of gadgets increased a lot. Some students felt that attention to students by faculty is not given properly and they had an easy-going attitude. Personal attention was missing. Most students faced connectivity or network issues and hence there was a disruption in learning. Then staying at home has its own share of distractions. They missed the class environment and over all a student life in the campus. The expected offline exposure is missing. Also, the sessions turned out to be less interactive as compared to the offline mode. A single student also commented on limited coverage of the syllabus. Another student did not like the power point presentation; according to the student it was traditional in approach. The lectures at times seemed long. They missed face to face interaction. A student felt bored as well and had no impact and felt he had no impact on his learning. There was lack of exposure. There was stress and pressure. It became hectic as well. It felt like it became static. Confidence and focus dipped. The student lacked self-motivation. Time management became an issue. Student did not get an e-book as well.

Hence, the present study gives an insight to the fact that over all the online mode of education helped in continuation of the education. The faculty, resources including the course and the platform had an impact on the satisfaction with online education. There were few factors like flexibility and accessibility as mentioned above that contributed positively and there were few like network and connectivity issues that requires improvement as mentioned above again.

Overall, the online teaching valuable when there was no option of continuing the education otherwise. Hence, we can easily say that the above-mentioned variables "Faculty Facilitation, Course Design and Platform Availability" has an impact on students' online process.

To study the Satisfaction level of management students with online education during Pandemic, interviews were also conducted to further validate the data collected in through Google forms. The duration of the interview was 6 to 8 minutes, and each student were told about the objective of the interview.

Profile of the Sample Respondents

The profile remains like the data collected through Google form. The section provides the basic information of the college students. The following table shows the output of the questions related to gender, age group, academic year, Level of study, the location of the College and whether the classes were held online or not. A structured questionnaire was developed in Word document.

The gender distribution showed the males respondents were 60% and female respondents were 40%. They were 100% post graduate management students. 100% mentioned that their college was in Gurugram. The students are justifiably distributed as per their academic year. 100% of the Second-year students were the respondents. The surveyed statistics showed the respondents were mostly in the age group between 20 and 25 years, 80% to be precise and 20% in the age group between 25 and 30 years 100% respondents mentioned that their classes are being held online.

Table 5 Demographics

Demographic Profile of the Students for the Interview		
Parameter		Percentage
Gender	Male	60%
	Female	40%
Post Graduate Management Student	Yes	100%
	No	NIL
Location: Gurgaon	Yes	100%
	No	NIL
Level of Study	First Year	NIL
	Second Year	100%
Age Group (in years)	Less than 20 years	NIL
	20-25 years	80%
	25-30 years	20%
	30-35 years	NIL
Are Management classes being held online?	Yes	100%
	No	NIL

Satisfaction level of management students with online education during Pandemic

When asked about how satisfied are the students with online education during pandemic ranging from (1) very dissatisfied to (5) very satisfied, most of the students 48% were neutral, 30% were satisfied, 11% were very dissatisfied, 8% were dissatisfied and 3% were very satisfied. If we see the percentages of the Google forms, we will find almost similar results. For example, 47% were neutral from the data collected through Google form.

The following is the analysis of **Faculty’s Facilitation**. When the students were asked to rate the quality of facilitation provided by faculty members ranging from (1) very dissatisfied to (5) very satisfied based on Likert Scale. A 20% of students mentioned that they were very satisfied, 30% were neutral, 6% were dissatisfied and 4% were very dissatisfied. 40% were satisfied which is quite close to the analyses of the satisfaction with the faculty’s data (38.8%) that was collected through the Google Form.

The most appealing factors included that the faculties were helpful, and every query were solved. The communication was not an issue and individual attention was given when required. The faculties had knowledge of their subject and the experience as well. However, interaction over zoom was not at appealing according to the few.

The following is the analysis of **Course Design** through online mode. When the students were asked about how would they rate the course design used in the college for the studies ranging from (1) very dissatisfied to (5) very satisfied? A 48% of students mentioned that they were satisfied, 28% were neutral, 14% were very satisfied and 6% were dissatisfied and 4% were very dissatisfied. If we compare the neutral aspect than it is close to what we analysed when I collected the data through Google form which was 26%.

When they were asked about the components they liked or disliked about the course design the students mentioned that they liked the study portal where the content was always available. The coverage and the structure were proper. They were able to take ownership of the course as well. However, a single student mentioned that the power point presentation did not make an impact as it was not appealing.

The following is the analysis of **Platform Availability**. When asked about how would they rate the usage of Zoom platform ranging from (1) very dissatisfied to (5) very satisfied? A 35% of students mentioned that they were very satisfied, 33% were neutral and 8% were very dissatisfied, 12% were very satisfied and 12% were dissatisfied. Again, the analysis for the data is very close to what was analysed in Google form for example, if we see the neutral aspect than in 29.12% was the average.

When further asked about what appeals to them most about Zoom Platform then the students mentioned that it is easier to use compared to other platforms and is efficient. They liked the features like the chat box and the option to change the background. The recording facility was also very appealing as it helped them to listen to the content whenever possible. However, when asked about what that is creates a glitch or trouble for them then they mentioned about voltage fluctuations because of which the internet does not work and there is also a lag of the video at times. The network issues were a cause of concern.

The next question was on to name few factors that led to the satisfaction and dissatisfaction with online education. This has been elaborately discussed in the content analysis for the same question in the Google form. Therefore, to validate the information the question was asked. The factors that led to satisfaction level were that the content was always available, the teachers were contactable anytime. The online portal was great. It was accessible and flexible. The students saved time and money as there was no travel involved. The course design was appropriate. The factors that led to the dissatisfaction were the students were not able to interact physically and hence they became a homebody. The practical aspects were a little difficult to understand. There was lack of few software.

Finally, the question on the choice of online mode, or would they prefer offline mode or may be hybrid, the 32% responded hybrid mode as they felt the hybrid mode was very convenient. The learning expectations would be met easily. The rest 24% mentioned online and 44% was in the favour of offline mode. Hence, the interview questions helped to reconfirm the analysis done through the data collected through Google form.

Findings

The first research question was “To study the satisfaction level of management students through online education during pandemic”. 47% were neutral and 31% were satisfied through the data collected from the Google form and 48% were neutral 30% were satisfied. The data is very close. Percentage analysis has been done and been presented in the paper already. This indicates that even when the education was shifted in online mode very quickly, a significant number of students took it positively. However, there are few factors that needs to be investigated (for example, sorting the issues related with technology) and which could form the base for the future study to improve the satisfaction percentage further as at present 11% were very dissatisfied and 8% were dissatisfied.

Few factors are important to check the influence on satisfaction or the dissatisfaction level of the students. A lot of work already has been done; few are mentioned in the Review of Literature portion. The next or second research question was “To study the factors that contribute to the satisfaction level of the students with online education.” Based on the data collection and the data analysis, the factors like accessibility and flexibility in terms of location, faculty’s facilitation, course structure and resource availability contributed to the satisfaction level. Further the influencing factors that led to satisfaction were Zoom platform to be precise, it was easy to use, and the recordings of the session were done easily. The faculties support and their interaction contributed further to the satisfaction level of the students. The faculties had to adjust to the new environment as well and learn the use of technology. Also, most of the students found it convenient as it was cost effective as well as it saved travelling expenses. Despite the fact, the online material had to be shifted almost with no notice, 45% through Google form and 48% through interview were satisfied the course design. The course design had to be modified to meet the requirements of the online learning which clearly show the students were accepted the course designed for their usage. Also, the use of platform, Zoom to be precise came out as a very important tool for the continuation of education through online mode. The students liked the usability and the recording facility especially. Hence, further it can form the base of the study as how much impact would zoom or any other platform have on the students’ learning experience. At present, the signs are very positive with the 37% from the data collected through Google form and 35% through the interview.

The third question was “To study the factors that contribute to the dissatisfaction level of the students with online education.” The hectic schedule, network issues, long hours of screen time and lack of practical exposure contributed to the dissatisfaction level. To identify the elements for satisfaction or dissatisfaction has become very complex. The construct is multifaceted. 6% showed that they were dissatisfied with the faculty’s facilitation as interaction over zoom was not at appealing according to the few. 6% was dissatisfied with the course design as the power point presentation did not make an impact especially. 12% through the interview, it was clear that they were dissatisfied with the platform availability. There were lags in the video when played. There were network issues. Hence, it is evident that at present the above-mentioned challenges are there and further opens the gate for more research work in order to improve the existing glitches.

Discussion of the Results

The present study not only highlights the factors contributing to the satisfaction levels of the students but also the factors that were not satisfactory. This will help the faculties to further strengthen the satisfactory contributors and improve on the areas of dissatisfactory contributors. The faculties will have a better insight of the factors and hence help them to work upon it further.

The present study derives the factors contributing to the satisfaction level of students with the online mode. The study explored the primary variables as Faculty’s facilitation, Course Design through online mode and Platform Availability. All these three play a very important role in the satisfaction level of the students with the online mode.

This means the faculty must understand the need of the student and deliver the content effectively. The faculty must communicate clearly for the better understanding of the students and must display enthusiasm through online mode. He or she should have complete knowledge of the subject he or she is teaching. The faculty should know the

usage of platform properly and create a comfortable learning space for the students. Individual attention leads to the satisfaction level of the students and feedback helps them to work on the areas of development. Therefore, from the current study, the faculty's support contributed most however the lack of use of technology affected the satisfaction level of students the most.

The second variable, Course Design affects the satisfaction level of the students as if the course is easily understood by the students without any problems, then it leads to the students' satisfaction. This means that the course structure should be designed to generate experience of different learning style. It should cover the syllabus appropriately and the provision of the content should be made available always. Now, from the above-mentioned analysis 42% agreed that the content was available in the form of notes and videos and 42% agreed the usage of webinar was apt and 51% agreed on the accountability for the students learning. The area of improvement would be to further work on ownership or accountability 9% felt that they were not satisfied. After delivering the course, if proper inputs or feedback is taken to design the course then it will help to design future courses.

The third variable Platform Availability has an impact over satisfaction levels of students as during pandemic the entire course was imparted through online mode as mentioned earlier. When the circumstances were not ordinary, an emphasis on the platform availability and its characteristics is important. This means that the Learnability is easy i.e., the steps of online teaching platform that student uses are easy to learn. Navigation system is easy. The recording facility is available. Rather 36% agreed that they were able to record the content. Platform also includes easy login and registration facility and other existing functions that should meet the expectations of the students that would further lead to the satisfaction of the students. 32% mentioned, the online mode was appealing in terms of visuals and videos. It should give ample opportunities to participate in the classroom discussion during online teaching. 39% were satisfied and mentioned that they got the opportunities. The satisfaction further leads to willingness to continue using the platform. 26% mentioned that they are willing to continue with online education and recommend it to others as well. This variable brings back our focus to the technology proficiency. This study not only brings forth the factors leading to satisfaction but also weaknesses of the online education platform. The positives will further help in significant contribution to the upgrading and optimization of online education and increasing the acceptance of online education.

This study hence helps to understand the current situation and areas of improvement for the future. Hence, the objectives to know the satisfaction level of the students and the factors contributing to the satisfaction and dissatisfaction level are understood from the above discussion.

Conclusion

The results of my study can be used to improve the areas where there are issues and work further to strengthen the system. A significant number also suggested the hybrid mode of learning as their preference. Narasimha Jayakumar (2021), mentions "Hybrid learning is here to stay. It is up to the education technologists to design learning environments that combine the best of both the in-person learning environment and the online learning space."

The importance of Faculty's facilitation, Course Design and Platform Availability have proved to be important determinants for the student satisfaction. Further the role of the faculty in terms of their communication, the structure of the course to provide different learning experiences and the uses of technology have been highlighted. Even though most of the students preferred offline mode of learning, the online learning comes with its own set of benefits. The outcome of the study has various important practical implications for the students, educators, and different researchers. The study has a very realistic approach to understand the students' expectation in the current setting. Despite the challenges, the online learning has surely paved a way into the future of education. It can be explored further as in how to leverage the benefits like technology and make the learning experience more effective and interesting.

Suggestions for the future Study

The research is conducted on the management students. Similar research can be done on students of different sectors like engineering students. Also, the survey can be conducted at different levels of study. In this study, only second year students were taken as a sample for data collection and analysis. At different levels the students' opinions and perceptions may differ a bit. Future study should be done to explore the different usages of technology and how does it affect the satisfaction level of the students. Also, the students' acceptance of online learning beyond pandemic can be further studied. Students have repeatedly mentioned about lack of practical exposure. Study can be further done to understand how it can be made effective and incorporate the practical lessons. The scope of the study can further reach different cities and states. More teachers and policy makers can be a part of the study as well. Also, what are the steps taken to improve the online education can be studied further especially in the areas of concern for example steps taken to improve the network issues or interaction of the faculty. Hence, it would be interesting to study the points mentioned above and explore any opportunities further.

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